

THE ADVANTAGES OF PARALLEL CORPUS BASES OF UZBEK-ENGLISH PROVERBS.

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***Abstract:** This article deals with opportunities of teaching proverbs through Russian National corpus, Sketch engine corpus and Uzbek-English paremias parallel corpora which is suggested by us.*

***Key words:** Proverb, corpus, parallel corpora, Russian National Corpus, Sketch engine, Uzbek-English paremias parallel corpora.*

INTRODUCTION

Proverbs expressing the people's culture, lifestyle, traditions and advice have been passed down from ancestors to generations for centuries. It is difficult to imagine our daily life without proverbs, because folk proverbs are widely used in our daily life, in songs, works of art, newspapers and magazines, and advertisements. In today's 21st century, when science and computer technologies are developing and the use of electronic resources is more advanced than books, teaching proverbs through computer technologies is a very effective method.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The most effective of these technologies is teaching proverbs through corpora, especially parallel corpora. Corpus linguistics is a branch of computer linguistics that deals with the development of general principles for the construction and use of linguistic corpora (text corpora) using computer technologies. A linguistic or linguistic corpus of texts (or usually just a corpus of texts) is a large, machine-readable, unified, structured, marked-up, philologically competent array of language data designed to solve specific linguistic problems.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Parallel corpuses of texts are composed of original texts in language A and translations of these texts into language B. For parallel corpora of texts, a number of subtypes are distinguished: 1) Texts in language A and their translations into language B; 2) Texts in languages A and B and their translations respectively into languages B and A; 3) Only translated texts in languages A, B, C,..., X, original texts were written in language D. In teaching proverbs, parallel corpora have greater opportunities than dictionaries. Proverb collections and dictionaries only help in a limited way. Without doubt they are a precious and essential part of cultural heritage. But these collections do not contain undisputable facts about the real use of a proverb in contemporary language or its constant changes and adaptations. Many proverbs will be passed on from collection to collection, from dictionary to dictionary and a collective example memory will be formed. This is unsatisfactory for second language learners who will be confronted with material that does not adequately reflect the current state of the language. Many corpora are collections of electronic texts which have been compiled to address a specific research question and are selected for parameters such as author, source, topic, text type, time period and medium. In our context these are special proverb corpora, e.g. searchable collections of texts or text excerpts from data bases which contain proverbs. Below we will consider the rendering of proverbs in some parallel corpora.

The screenshot shows the 'PARALLEL CONCORDANCE' interface for the 'United Nations Parallel Corpus – English'. The search term is 'simple Better late than never' with 9 results. The interface displays a table of results with columns for document ID, English text, and Russian text. The Russian text is highlighted in yellow. The interface includes navigation icons, a search bar, and a 'SUBSCRIBE' button.

Doc ID	English Text	Russian Text
doc#5485	<S> Better late than never : " By following the river you reach the sea " , said Plautus as long ago as the second century B.C. To this end , despite the democratic structures set up by Solon and Pittacus in the sixth century B.C. , it was necessary to wait for Ephialtes , Cleisthenes and Pericles to achieve the democratization of political life in Athens . </S>	<S> Лучше поздно , чем никогда : " Идя по реке , дойдешь до моря " , сказал Плавт много лет назад , во втором столетии до нашей эры . </S><S> Для этого , несмотря на демократические структуры , основанные Солонем и Питтаком в шестом веке до нашей эры , нужно было дождаться Эфиалта , Клифена и Перикла , чтобы добиться демократизации политической жизни в Афинах . </S>
doc#12782	<S> Better late than never , I suppose . </S>	<S> Полагаю , что лучше поздно , чем никогда . </S>
doc#41024	<S> The time to do so may be long overdue , but it is better late than never . </S>	<S> Возможно , это следовало бы сделать гораздо раньше , однако лучше позже , чем никогда . </S>
doc#52971	<S> One might say that it was about time , and one would certainly be right , but better late than never . </S>	<S> Кто-то мог бы сказать , что уже давно пора , и он , безусловно , был бы прав , но лучше поздно , чем никогда . </S>
doc#77032	<S> We are encouraged to learn about the broad range of internal reform measures , some of which are long overdue -- but better late than never -- that the Secretary-General is planning to implement . </S>	<S> нас ободряет широкий диапазон мер по внутренней реформе , часть из которых давно назрели -- но лучше поздно , чем никогда , -- которые Генеральный секретарь планирует осуществить . </S>
	<S> We simply cannot be satisfied with a " better late than never " , when in 1987 , exactly 20 years ago , President Maumoon Abdul Gayoom of the Republic of the Maldives alerted us that he did not come to speak about	<S> Мы просто не можем успокаивать себя словами < < лучше поздно , чем никогда > > , памятуя о том , что в 1987 году , ровно 20 лет назад , президент Мальдивской Республики гн Момвн Абдвл

Sketch engine parallel concordance

The provision of proverbs in two and more languages with this corpus is covered by resources. By clicking on each resource, information about the sentences in the text, the number of words and the year the text was created will be provided. This way you can sort proverbs by years. All texts here are taken from real situations. Such opportunities are available in all parallel bases. The proverbs are given in Russian national corpus below.

Объем всего корпуса: 6 384 документа, 161 253 884 слова.

Слово 1: "внешность"
 Слово 2: "обманчива" на расстоянии 1 от Слова 1

Найдено: 9 документов, 9 вхождений.

Поискать в других корпусах: [основном](#), [многоязычном](#).

Страницы: 1

1. Peter Thunborg. LISTA: De snabbaste helikoptrarna i världen [www.expressen.se] (21.11.2016) | Самые быстрые вертолеты в мире (https://inosmi.ru/military/20161124/238272342.html, 24.11.2016) [омонимия не снята] [Все примеры \(1\)](#)

swe	De kan se ut som gigantiska humlor som surrar i luften men skenet bedrar. [Peter Thunborg. LISTA: De snabbaste helikoptrarna i världen [www.expressen.se] (21.11.2016) Самые быстрые вертолеты в мире (https://inosmi.ru/military/20161124/238272342.html, 24.11.2016)] [омонимия не снята] <--->
rus	Они похожи на гигантских жуужащих шмелей, но внешность обманчива . [Peter Thunborg. LISTA: De snabbaste helikoptrarna i världen [www.expressen.se] (21.11.2016) Самые быстрые вертолеты в мире (https://inosmi.ru/military/20161124/238272342.html, 24.11.2016)] [омонимия не снята] <--->
2. Danny Wattin. Herr Isakowitz skatt (2014) | Динни Ваттин. Сокровище господина Исаковича (А. В. Савицкая, 2015) [омонимия не снята] [Все примеры \(1\)](#)

swe	Men skenet bedrar, för Ruth, visade det sig, var inte alls lugn och stillsam. [Danny Wattin. Herr Isakowitz skatt (2014) Динни Ваттин. Сокровище господина Исаковича (А. В. Савицкая, 2015)] [омонимия не снята] <--->
rus	Впрочем, внешность обманчива , поскольку Рут, как оказалось, отнюдь не была тихой и спокойной. [Danny Wattin. Herr Isakowitz skatt (2014) Динни Ваттин. Сокровище господина Исаковича (А. В. Савицкая, 2015)] [омонимия не снята] <--->

Russian national corpus

In this corpus, the Russian and German variants of the proverb **внешность обманчива** are given based on sources from real situations.

The provision of proverbs in the parallel corpus of Uzbek-English paremiias that we offer is as follows.

Чучварани хом санама	
Search	Clean

Ўзбек тилида
Чучварани хом санама.

Инглиз тилида
Don't count your,chickens before they are hatched

Маъноси
Ўзбек тилида
Бу мақол ҳақиқатан ҳам содир бўлганлигини билишдан олдин яхши бир воқеа содир бўлишига боғлиқ режалар тузмаслик кераклигини англатади.

Маъноси
Инглиз тилида
This proverb means that you should not make plans that depend on something good happening before you know that it has actually happened.

Вариантлари (мақоллар мисолида)
Ўзбек тилида
Чучварани хом санама, санамай сакктз дема.

Вариантлари (мақоллар мисолида)
Инглиз тилида
Reckon your cbllckens after they are hatched.

Синоними
Ўзбек тилида
Чучварани пишириб сана, Жўжани — очириб.

Синоними
Инглиз тилида
First catch your hare, then cook him. Gut no fish till you got them. Don't halloo till you are out of the wood.

Мисоллар	
Uzbek	English
<p>Чучварани хом санабсизлар! Уйимга бостириб кириб, мени ўдирмоқчи бўлганларинг учун ўзларингни судга бераман, — деб шовқин солиб қолдилар қори поччам, — ҳали сизлар мени билмас экансизлар...Худойберди Тўхтабоев сарик девни миниб 156-бет</p>	<p>Don't count your chickens before they are hatched! I will sue you for broke into my house and tried to kill me , you don't know me yet. - my qori brother-in-law said noisily. Hudoyberdi Tukhtabaev Riding a yellow genie p. 156</p>
<p>Қарши томондан сертупроқ йўлни чангитиб бир отлиқ кела бошлади! Бошида мис қалқону қўлтиғида найза. Дадил бўл, Акбарий, найзангни ўнг қўлга ол, қиличинг чап ёнингда, дея шивирлаб отнинг бошини тортдим. Суворий қиёфасида келаётган ёвуз душман Сехргар Иблисинг айнан ўзи бўлиши ҳам мумкин. Кўз юмиб-очгунча остидаги отни ешакка айлантириб, ўзи ёш бола қиёфасига кириб олди. Демак, ўша! Оббо лаънати-ей, қувлигини қаранг, бир сонияда ҳаммасини ўзгартириб юборади-я. Чучварани хом</p>	<p>On the opposite side, a horseman began to come, dusting the dirt road! There were copper shield on his head and spear in his armpit. Take courage. Akbari, take the spear in your right hand and your sword in your left, I whispered and pulled the horse's head. The evil enemy coming in the form of a cavalryman may also be the magician devil himself. In the blink of an eye, he turned the horse under him into a donkey and took himself on the appearance of a young boy . So that's it! God Damn it, look at the sly, it will change everything in a second. Reckon</p>

<p>санабсан, Иблис! Худойберди Тўхтабоев Ширин Қовунлар малакатида 1-жилд 283-бет</p>	<p>your cblckens after they are hatched. Devil! Hudoyberdi Tukhtabaev In the kingdom of sweet melons 1-volume p.283</p>
<p>Ёлгон айтасан, ёлгон! Кузингдан билиб турибман... Булмасам, бузамиз деганимда, нимага хуп демадинг? Йук, ука, чучварани хом санама... Мен нимагадир эътибор килмаганман-а! Лекин сен... сен эмас, энанг хам, отанг хам, бобонг хам биласизлар бунинг тарихини! Бундаги чирокни энанг ёкмаганига мени кандай килиб ишонтироласан? Ёки булмасам, шу ердан отанг ўтаётганда, фотиха ўкимаганига кимни кафил килоласан?! А? Ана шундай! Мени алдай олмайсан! Шукур Холмирзаев Сайланма хикоялар тўплам 1-жилд</p>	<p>You're lying, you're lying! I know from your eyes. when I say we break, why did not you say okay ? Not , brother. Gut no flsh till you got them.... I didn't notice anything! But not only you, your mother, father and grandfather know the history of this! How can you convince me that your mother didn't like the lamp? Or, who can you guarantee that your father did not recite the Fatiha while he was passing by ?! A? That's it! You can't fool me! Shukur Kholmiraev Selected stories collection 1 vol</p>
<p>Зухра. Мен чаласавод, сенинг саводинг росами? Бир кўзинг одамларнинг тишида, бир кўзинг чўнтагида-ку, яна қайси кўзинг билан ўқиб савод чиқаргансан? М а р а с у л (Насибага). Чучварани хом санама, мендан ялчиб алимент ололмайсан! Насиба . Кераги йўқ! Зуҳ ра. Қонун товукдай қийқиллатиб олиб беради! Марасул . Қонунга мувофиқ оладими? Ойлиги юз сўмлик ишга кираман! Зуҳра. Ҳезалак! Абдулла Қаҳҳор Оғрик тишлар комедияси</p>	<p>Zukhra: I am half-educated , are you educated? One eye is on people's teeth, one eye is in your pocket, which else have you read literacy with your eyes? Mirasul (to Nasib). Don't count your,chickens before they are hatched! You can't get aliment from me! Nasiba: No need! Zukhra: The law makes you cluck like a chicken! Mirasul: Will she take aliment according to the law? I get a job for a hundred sums a month! Zukhra: Effeminate! Abdullah Kakhor "Sick Teeth" comedy</p>

<p>— Сиз яқинда одамгарчиликдан ҳам чиқасиз.</p> <p>— Хўп, ука, — кулимсиради Амирқул ака. — Сен жўжадан шу гапларни эшитдим-а. Ҳа, майли! Хор бўлдиқда, а? Йў-ўқ. Чучварани хом санама, чироғим! Биласанми, дунё кенг! Бу ер тўғри келмаса, бошқа ер бор. Совет ҳукуматининг ери кўп! Шукур Холмирзаев Тикан орасидаги одам (ҳикоя)</p>	<p>-You will soon lose your humanity as well.</p> <p>-Well, brother, -smiles older brother Amirkul.</p> <p>I heard that from you , the chicken.</p> <p>Yes, that's right! We were humiliated, no. Don't count your,chickens before they are hatched, dear ! You know, the world is wide!</p> <p>If this place is not right, there is another place. There are a lot of places in Soviet government</p> <p>Shukur Kholmirzayev The man between the thorns (story)</p>
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CONCLUSION

When teaching proverbs through this corpus database, the language learner receives the following information:

- proverbs in Uzbek-English, English-Uzbek languages
- the meaning of proverbs in Uzbek-English, English-Uzbek languages
- synonym of proverbs in Uzbek-English, English-Uzbek languages
- variants of proverbs in Uzbek-English, English-Uzbek languages
- examples of the use of proverbs in Uzbek-English, English-Uzbek languages in literary texts.

In conclusion, the parallel corpus bases are given more chances to teach proverbs such as meanings, synonyms, variants and examples of using proverbs than proverbs dictionary. The provision of this information in two languages further increases its opportunities.

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